

EKG SIGNALLARINI XOS SON VA XOS VEKTORLAR ASOSIDA KOMPYUTERLI MODELLASHTIRISH

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada elektrokardiogramma (EKG) signallarini statistik tahlil qilish masalasi ko'rib chiqilgan. Tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi EKG signallaridan ajratib olingan muhim parametrlar asosida kovariatsiya matritsasini tuzish hamda uning xos sonlari va xos vektorlarini hisoblash orqali signallarning asosiy xususiyatlarini aniqlashdan iborat. Xos sonlar yordamida EKG signallaridagi axborot taqsimoti baholanib, eng muhim komponentlar tanlab olindi. Xos vektorlar esa signal fazosini yangi o'qlarga proyeksiyalash imkonini berib, ma'lumotlar o'lchamini kamaytirish va tahlilni soddalashtirishga xizmat qildi. Olingan natijalar EKG signallarini qayta ishlash, diagnostik tahlil va yurak faoliyatini baholash jarayonlarida statistik yondashuvlarning samaradorligini ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqot natijalari biotibbiy signallarni tahlil qilish sohasida qo'llanilishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: Elektrokardiogramma, EKG signali, statistik tahlil, xos son, xos vektor, kovariatsiya matritsasi, asosiy komponentlar tahlili, signalni qayta ishlash

Kirish. Elektrokardiogramma (EKG) signallari yurak faoliyatini baholashda eng muhim va keng qo'llaniladigan noinvaziv diagnostik vositalardan biri hisoblanadi. EKG yordamida yurak ritmi, impulslarning o'tish tezligi hamda yurak mushaklarining funksional holati haqida muhim klinik axborot olinadi. Shu sababli EKG signallarini qayta ishlash va tahlil qilish masalalari zamonaviy tibbiyot va biotibbiy muhandislik sohalarida alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi [1, 2]. EKG signallari murakkab tuzilishga ega bo'lib, ularning tarkibida foydali axborot bilan bir qatorda turli xil shovqinlar va artefaktlar ham mavjud bo'ladi. Bunday holatlar signalni an'anaviy vizual tahlil qilishni qiyinlashtiradi hamda aniq diagnostik xulosalar chiqarishga to'sqinlik qiladi. Shu bois EKG signallarini tahlil qilishda matematik va statistik usullardan foydalanish zarurati yuzaga keladi [2]. Biotibbiy signallarni qayta ishlashda statistik yondashuvlar muhim o'rin tutadi. Xususan, kovariatsiya matritsasiga asoslangan tahlil usullari

signalning ichki tuzilmasini ochib berish imkonini beradi. Kovariatsiya matritsasining xos sonlari va xos vektorlari signaldagi axborot taqsimotini baholash hamda asosiy xususiyatlarni ajratib olishda samarali vosita hisoblanadi [3].

Asosiy komponentlar tahlili (Principal Component Analysis, PCA) xos son va xos vektorlar yordamida amalga oshiriladigan klassik statistik usullardan biri bo'lib, u yuqori o'lchamli ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilishda keng qo'llaniladi. PCA yordamida signaldagi eng muhim komponentlar aniqlanadi, ma'lumotlar o'lchami kamaytiriladi va ortiqcha bog'liqliklar bartaraf etiladi [3,4]. Ushbu yondashuv EKG signallarini tahlil qilishda diagnostik ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan parametrlarni aniqlash imkonini beradi.

So'nggi yillarda EKG signallarini PCA va xos sonlar asosida tahlil qilishga oid ko'plab ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borilmoqda. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, xos sonlar spektri orqali signaldagi

asosiy axborot ulushini baholash, xos vektorlar orqali esa signalni yangi koordinata fazosiga proyeksiyalash mumkin [5]. Bu esa yurak faoliyatidagi o‘zgarishlarni aniqlash, shuningdek, shovqin va artefaktlarni kamaytirishda samarali hisoblanadi.

Mazkur maqolada EKG signallaridan ajratib olingan parametrlar asosida kovariatsiya matritsasi tuzilib, uning xos sonlari va xos vektorlari hisoblandi. Olingan natijalar asosida EKG signallarining asosiy xususiyatlari tahlil qilindi hamda statistik yondashuvlarning biotibbiy signal tahlilidagi samaradorligi baholandi. Ushbu tadqiqot natijalari EKG signallarini qayta ishlash va yurak faoliyatini baholash bilan bog‘liq amaliy masalalarda qo‘llanilishi mumkin.

Adabiyotlar tahlili. Elektrokardiogramma (EKG) yurakning elektr faolligini invaziv bo‘lmagan usulda qayd etib, aritmiyalarni aniqlash va yurak faoliyatini kuzatishda keng qo‘llaniladi. EKG signali P, QRS va T to‘lqinlaridan iborat bo‘lib, yurak ritmidagi buzilishlarni aniqlash imkonini beradi. Aritmiya hayot uchun xavfli bo‘lib, yurak xuruji va to‘satdan infarktga sabab bo‘lishi mumkin[6-7].

So‘nggi yillarda EKG signallarini tahlil qilishda mashinali o‘rganishga asoslangan avtomatik klassifikatsiya usullari keng rivojlandi. Ushbu yondashuvlarda SVM, KNN, Random Forest, LSTM va boshqa algoritmlar qo‘llanilib, xususiyatlarni ajratish va klassifikatsiya aniqligini oshirishga qaratilgan[8-10].

Biroq EKG signallarining murakkabligi, individual farqlar va mavjud ma‘lumotlar to‘plamlarining cheklanganligi aritmiyalarni aniq va ishonchli klassifikatsiya qilishda muhim muammolarni keltirib chiqarmoqda[11-13].

KPCA turli tadqiqotlarda samarali qo‘llanilgan. U EKG va nafas olish signallari o‘rtasidagi chiziqsiz bog‘liqlikni aniqlab, aniqlik va hisoblash samaradorligini oshiradi [14]. Wavelet usullari bilan birgalikda qo‘llanilganda yuqori klassifikatsiya aniqligi ta‘minlangan [15]. Shuningdek, SVM bilan birga xususiyat ajratishda yuqori sezgirlik va aniqlik natijalari olingan [16]. SVR asosidagi aritmiya aniqlashda ham KPCA

klassifikatsiya samaradorligini oshirgan [17]. KPCA EKG signallarining chiziqsiz va chiziqsiz xususiyatlarini kamaytirib, 5 ta asosiy komponent bilan 90% dan ortiq axborotni saqlab qoladi va bu uni oddiy PCA ga nisbatan ustun ekanini ko‘rsatadi [18].

Naive Bayes algoritmi ham EKG signallari asosida yurak kasalliklarini tasniflashda keng qo‘llanilgan. [19] tadqiqotda u PT, BPM va RR intervallari kabi EKG xususiyatlari asosida aritmiyalarni aniqlash uchun ishlatilgan [20]. Empirik modali ajratish (EMD) va PCA yordamida signal qayta ishlangach, xususiyatlar ajratilib, yurak anomaliyalarini aniqlash amalga oshirilgan. [21] da Naive Bayes tachikardiya va bradikardiya kabi turli aritmiyalarni tasniflashda xususiyat tanlash usullari bilan birga qo‘llanilgan. Shuningdek, [22] RR intervallari va boshqa statistik xususiyatlar asosida aritmiya turlarini aniqlashda Naive Bayesdan foydalangan. [23] da esa u boshqa algoritmlar bilan birgalikda qo‘llanilib, turli yurak aritmiyalarini aniqlashga xizmat qilgan.

[24] tadqiqotda yurak kasalliklarini aniqlash uchun LSTM modeli klassifikator sifatida, shovqinni kamaytirish va xususiyat ajratish uchun esa Continuous Wavelet Transform (CWT) usuli qo‘llangan. Ushbu yondashuv EKG signallaridan muhim xususiyatlarni samarali ajratib olish va yuqori aniqlikda tasniflash imkonini bergan (o‘qitishda 98.4%, testda 94.42%).

Signal sifatini yaxshilash va shovqinni kamaytirish uchun furye qatori ishlatilgan [25]. EKG signallari bitta kanal asosida tahlil qilinib, RR intervallari, signal morfologiyasi va statistik xususiyatlar orqali aritmiyalar aniqlangan [26].

Zamonaviy tibbiyotda EKG signallarini sonli qayta ishlash va statistik tahlil qilish usullari tobora muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. An‘anaviy usulda baholashga nisbatan kompyuter yordamidagi tahlil usullari aniqroq, tezroq va takrorlanadigan natijalar berishi isbotlangan. Biroq EKG ma‘lumotlarining yuqori o‘lchamli tabiat (12 ta bo‘lma \times chastota) va ko‘p qatorli korrelyatsiyalar klassik statistik usullarni bevosita qo‘llashni murakkablashtiradi. Shu sababli ko‘p o‘lchamli statistik usullar, xususan, asosiy

komponentlar tahlili (Principal Component Analysis, PCA) EKG signallarini qayta ishlashda keng qo'llanila boshlandi. EKG signallarining statistik tahlili bir nechta muhim klinik va texnik muammolarni hal etishga yordam beradi. iqligini oshirishi ko'rsatilgan.

Masalaning qo'yilishi. Biz tajriba natijalari sifatida 625 vaqt intervalidan iborat amplitudalarning son qiymatlari asosida xos son va xos vektorlar asosida matritsaviy tahlil o'tkazamiz. Yurakning chap va o'ng bo'lmalardagi parametrlarni quyidagicha belgilash kiritib olamiz:

I - x_1 , II - x_2 , III - x_3 , aVR - x_4 , aVL - x_5 , aVF - x_6 , V1 - x_7 , V2 - x_8 , V3 - x_9 , V4 - x_{10} , V5 - x_{11} , V6 - x_{12} .

Yuqoridagi almashtirishlar kiruvchi omillar hisoblanadi. Kiruvchi omillar asosida 625×12 o'lchamdagi X matritsani quyidagicha yozib olamiz:

$$X = \begin{pmatrix} x_{1,1} - \bar{x}_1 & x_{2,1} - \bar{x}_2 & \dots & x_{12,1} - \bar{x}_{12} \\ x_{1,2} - \bar{x}_1 & x_{2,2} - \bar{x}_2 & \dots & x_{12,2} - \bar{x}_{12} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{1,625} - \bar{x}_1 & x_{2,625} - \bar{x}_2 & \dots & x_{12,625} - \bar{x}_{12} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

bunda

$$\bar{x}_i = \frac{1}{625} \sum_{k=1}^{625} x_{i,k}; \quad i = \overline{1,12} \quad (2)$$

(1) matritsa asosida kovariatsiya matritsasini tuzib olishimiz kerak, buning uchun ushbu kovariatsiya matritsasining elementlarini quyidagi formula orqali topamiz:

$$c_{i,j} = \frac{1}{625-1} \sum_{k=1}^{625} ((x_{i,k} - \bar{x}_i)(x_{j,k} - \bar{x}_j)); \quad i, j = \overline{1,12} \quad (2)$$

bunda $c_{i,j} = c_{j,i}; \quad i, j = \overline{1,12}$.

Natijada quyidagi xarakteristik matritsaga kelamiz:

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} c_{1,1} & c_{1,2} & \dots & c_{1,12} \\ c_{2,1} & c_{2,2} & \dots & c_{2,12} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ c_{12,1} & c_{12,2} & \dots & c_{12,12} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

(3) xarakteristik matritsa elementlarining son qiymatlarini quyidagi jadval orqali ifodalaymiz:

1-jadval. Xarakteristik matritsa elementlarining son qiymatlari jadvali

	I	II	III	aVR	aVL	aVF
I	0,019448	0,023804	0,012482	-0,019178	0,007961	0,016639
II	0,023804	0,029707	0,014481	-0,023839	0,008561	0,020694
III	0,012482	0,014481	0,009256	-0,011810	0,006919	0,010325
aVR	-0,019178	-0,023839	-0,011810	0,019208	-0,007160	-0,016585
aVL	0,007961	0,008561	0,006919	-0,007160	0,005947	0,006220
aVF	0,016639	0,020694	0,010325	-0,016585	0,006220	0,014551
V1	0,003618	-0,000302	0,009993	-0,000044	0,012053	0,001454
V2	0,013960	0,013942	0,013673	-0,011623	0,012482	0,010512
V3	0,025571	0,029934	0,018239	-0,024366	0,013228	0,021010
V4	0,033910	0,041610	0,021364	-0,033579	0,013442	0,028755
V5	0,036364	0,045531	0,021749	-0,036509	0,012579	0,031402
V6	0,029006	0,036649	0,016946	-0,029307	0,009393	0,025295

	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5	V6
I	0,003618	0,013960	0,025571	0,033910	0,036364	0,029006
II	-0,000302	0,013942	0,029934	0,041610	0,045531	0,036649
III	0,009993	0,013673	0,018239	0,021364	0,021749	0,016946
aVR	-0,000044	-0,011623	-0,024366	-0,033579	-0,036509	-0,029307
aVL	0,012053	0,012482	0,013228	0,013442	0,012579	0,009393
aVF	0,001454	0,010512	0,021010	0,028755	0,031402	0,025295
V1	0,054808	0,032688	0,015316	0,003030	-0,001953	-0,003499
V2	0,032688	0,028554	0,025599	0,022857	0,019938	0,014303
V3	0,015316	0,025599	0,036927	0,044543	0,045572	0,035526
V4	0,003030	0,022857	0,044543	0,059960	0,064467	0,051358
V5	-0,001953	0,019938	0,045572	0,064467	0,071425	0,057551
V6	-0,003499	0,014303	0,035526	0,051358	0,057551	0,046600

Masalaning sonli yechimi va uning natijalari. Eng avvalo ushbu 12 (12 ta kiruvchi omil) empirik kuzatuv natijalari asosida (3) xarakteristik matritsa uchun xos sonni topishga nisbatan quyidagi matritsani hosil qilamiz:

$$C - \lambda E = \begin{pmatrix} c_{1,1} & c_{1,2} & \dots & c_{1,12} \\ c_{2,1} & c_{2,2} & \dots & c_{2,12} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ c_{12,1} & c_{12,2} & \dots & c_{12,12} \end{pmatrix} - \lambda \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} c_{1,1} - \lambda & c_{1,2} & \dots & c_{1,12} \\ c_{2,1} & c_{2,2} - \lambda & \dots & c_{2,12} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ c_{12,1} & c_{12,2} & \dots & c_{12,12} - \lambda \end{pmatrix}; \quad (4)$$

(4) matritsaning determinantini 0 ga tenglashtirsak, quyidagi 12-tartibli ko'phadli tenglamaga kelamiz:

$$\det(C - \lambda E) = \begin{vmatrix} c_{1,1} - \lambda & c_{1,2} & \dots & c_{1,12} \\ c_{2,1} & c_{2,2} - \lambda & \dots & c_{2,12} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ c_{12,1} & c_{12,2} & \dots & c_{12,12} - \lambda \end{vmatrix} = b_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{12} b_i \lambda^i = 0; \quad (5)$$

(5) tenglamani yechsak, quyidagi qiymatlarni olamiz:

$$\lambda_1=0,309171491; \quad \lambda_2=0,081446779; \quad \lambda_3=0,004391721; \quad \lambda_4=0,001160752; \quad \lambda_5=0,000221138;$$

$\lambda_6=0,000000001$; $\lambda_7=0,000000001$; $\lambda_8=0,000000001$;
 $\lambda_9=\lambda_{10}=\lambda_{11}=\lambda_{12}=0$.

Ushbu xos sonlarning qiymatlaridan ko‘rinib turibdiki, asosan λ_1 , λ_2 va λ_3 lar eng ko‘p ta‘sir etuvchi omillar ekan.

II, V4, V5, V6 bo‘lmalar uchun λ_1 xos son, V1, V2 va V3 bo‘lmalar uchun λ_2 xos son, aVR, aVL va aVF bo‘lmalar uchun λ_3 xos sonlar xarakterlovchi xos sonlar hisoblanadi.

λ_1 xos son uchun xos vektor quyidagi tenglamani yechish orqali topiladi:

$$\det(C - \lambda_1 E)v_1 = 0; \quad (6)$$

(6) tenglamaning yechimi quyidagiga teng bo‘ladi:

$$v_1 = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} -0.250195, -0.305422, -0.161523, 0.246176, \\ -0.103865, -0.212942, -0.055665, -0.183284, \\ -0.331315, -0.43816, -0.471071, -0.375422. \end{array} \right\} \quad (7)$$

λ_2 xos son uchun xos vektor quyidagi tenglamani yechish orqali topiladi:

$$\det(C - \lambda_2 E)v_2 = 0; \quad (8)$$

(8) tenglamaning yechimi quyidagiga teng bo‘ladi:

$$v_2 = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} -0.008485, -0.086756, 0.114513, 0.062711, \\ 0.165060, -0.037032, 0.804317, 0.463874, \\ 0.161486, -0.061638, -0.164655, -0.16627. \end{array} \right\} \quad (9)$$

λ_3 xos son uchun xos vektor quyidagi tenglamani yechish orqali topiladi:

$$\det(C - \lambda_3 E)v_3 = 0; \quad (10)$$

(10) tenglamaning yechimi quyidagiga teng bo‘ladi:

$$v_3 = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} -0.057426, 0.057332, -0.127152, 0.035898, \\ -0.242251, 0.097779, 0.51397, -0.378462, \\ -0.428302, -0.210776, 0.32017, 0.412234. \end{array} \right\} \quad (11)$$

Xulosa. Xulosa sifatida shuni aytish mumkinki, boshqa mualliflarning ko‘plab tadqiqotlaridan farqli o‘laroq, ushbu maqolada xos sonlar yordamida EKG signallaridagi axborot taqsimoti baholanib, eng muhim komponentlar tanlab olindi. Jumladan $\lambda_1 = 0.3092$ – signalning 78% ini tashkil qiladi. Bu global yurak mushagi

hujayralarining elektr jihatdan harakatlanishi hisobiga asosiy qon haydovchi bo‘limning (ya‘ni, II, V4, V5 va V6) faollashishi hisoblanadi. Bu normal yurak uchun kutilgan holat. $\lambda_2 = 0.0815 - 20.5\%$. V1 (0.804) va V2 (0.464) ning eng yuqori yuklamasi – anterior septal va o‘ng qorincha komponenti. Ikkinchi komponent birgalikda PC1 bilan 98.5% ni qoplaydi. $\lambda_3 = 0.0044 - 1.1\%$. Yurakning pastki va yon qismlari orasida sezilarli farq bor degan ma‘noni anglatadi. $\lambda_6 - \lambda_{12} = 0$ – Bu Eyndxoven qonunining matematik tasdiqi (III = II – I, aVR/aVL/aVF ulardan kelib chiqadi). Bu esa apparatura va signal sifatining mukammal ekanligini ko‘rsatadi.

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